

PEMANFAATAN *BLENDED LEARNING* UNTUK MENINGKATKAN EFEKTIVITAS BELAJAR GOOGLE SPREADSHEET PADA BIMBINGAN TEKNOLOGI INFORMATIKA DAN KOMUNIKASI

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk memperbaiki proses pembelajaran sehingga meningkatkan efektivitas belajar dengan pemanfaatan *blended learning*. Bentuk penelitian adalah penelitian tindakan kelas. Penelitian dilaksanakan di kelas X PIPS 1 SMA Negeri 2 Pontianak yang terdiri dari 35 orang. Pengumpulan data menggunakan lembar observasi yang dilakukan rekan pendidik saat proses pembelajaran tatap muka, soal evaluasi (daring), dan memberikan angket ke peserta didik. Teknik analisis data yang digunakan adalah analisis deskriptif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa pengelolaan pembelajaran meningkat dari siklus I ke siklus II; hasil belajar peserta didik pada materi Google Spreadsheet meningkat dari siklus I ke siklus II; dan peserta didik memberikan respons positif mengenai pemanfaatan *blended learning* dalam proses pembelajaran. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, disimpulkan bahwa *blended learning* meningkatkan efektivitas belajar peserta didik.

Kata Kunci: *blended learning*; Google Spreadsheet; efektivitas belajar.

Abstract

The research aimed to improve the learning process so as to increase the effectiveness of learning by utilizing blended learning. The form of research was classroom action research. The research was conducted in class X PIPS 1 SMA Negeri 2 Pontianak which consisted of 35 students. Data collection used observation sheets carried out by fellow educators during the face-to-face learning process, evaluation questions (online), and giving questionnaires to students. The data analysis technique used descriptive analysis. The results showed that learning management increased from cycle I to cycle II; student learning outcomes on Google Spreadsheet material increased from cycle I to cycle II; and students gave positive responses regarding the use of blended learning in the learning process. Based on the results of the research, it was concluded that blended learning increases the learning effectiveness of students.

Keywords: *blended learning*; Google Spreadsheet; learning effectiveness.